

Determination of Optimal Values for Polycarboxylate and Melamine Sulfonate-Based Superplasticisers in High-Strength Mortar Production

Burak Şahin*^{ORCID}, Lütfullah Gündüz^{ORCID}

İzmir Kâtip Çelebi University, Department of Civil Engineering, İzmir, Türkiye

*İletişimden sorumlu yazar: 1996buraksahin@gmail.com

Abstract

The superior properties of superplasticizer additives in increasing the workability of mortar mixtures, reducing water content, controlling setting times and providing high strength performance and which type of additive produces more effective results are an important subject of investigation. While the application of these additives to concrete is somewhat familiar, their use in cement-based mortar designs is a relatively new topic and there is not enough information regarding their effectiveness in mortars. In this study, the technical properties of alternative mortar mixtures created using different new generation superplasticizers such as polycarboxylate and melamine sulfonate were comparatively analyzed experimentally. Within the scope of the study, two series of self-compacting mortar combination mixtures with 20% and 30% cement by weight, using each additive type, were designed and a total of eight alternative mixture combinations were tested. In the mixture designs, mortar samples were prepared with polycarboxylate-based additives at 0.47% and 0.55% of the cement weight. Additionally, mortar samples were prepared with melamine sulfonate-based additives at 1.5% and 2.0% of the cement weight. Separate test samples were prepared for each mortar design and technical values such as consistency, self-leveling properties, density of each mixture and mechanical strength, capillarity, water absorption by mass and apparent porosity values of the hardened mortar samples were analyzed.

Keywords: Polycarboxylate, melamine sulfonate, superplasticiser, self-compacting, properties

1. Introduction

Concrete, as the main composite building material, due to its high durability and operational reliability is widely used in construction [1]. It has widespread applications in different spheres of infrastructure, and sometimes ordinary concrete alone may not withstand certain adverse conditions due to its lesser longevity and lower strength. Therefore, chemical or mineral admixtures are applied to enhance the properties of the concrete. The properties of the concrete are affected differently by different admixtures [2,3]. Admixtures have been used in the concrete industry for many decades. They were usually by-products of particular primary material production that eventually found an application as a concrete admixture. Since its composition and hence its properties can only be modified within narrow limits, its performance in concrete is limited [4]. Chemical additives continue to play a crucial role in modern concrete. Until recently, the most important technological improvements in concrete technology came from the introduction of innovative additives, while cement production itself has matured somewhat and focused more on waste management to contribute to a closed-loop economy [5,6,7].

Superplasticisers are chemical admixtures that can be considered to pertain to the category of polymeric dispersants and used in the construction industry to improve the flow and the workability of concrete and mortar, making them indispensable components of modern construction. They have been in use for decades, and their history dates back to the early 20th century [8]. In terms of chemical structure, superplasticisers can be broadly classified into two general categories. The first category, the sulfonate-based superplasticisers, are the most important group of superplasticisers currently in use in the concrete industry. The first and most widely accepted compounds of this group are the polynaphthalene sulfonates [9]. Polymelamine sulfonates are a second family of sulfonated superplasticisers that are also widely used in the concrete industry [9]. Super plasticizers are used where well-dispersed particle suspension is required to improve the flow characteristics (rheology) of suspensions such as in concrete applications. Their addition to concrete or mortar allows the reduction of the water to cement ratio without negatively affecting the workability of the mixture, and enables

the production of self-consolidating concrete and high performance concrete. They greatly improve the performance of the hardening fresh paste. The strength of concrete increases, as the water to cement ratio decreases. Superplasticisers are synthetic polymers [10]. Superplasticisers are also can be used to increase compressive strength. It increases the workability of concrete and reduces the need for water content by 15-30% [11]. The purpose of plasticizing admixtures is to reduce the water content in the concrete while maintaining its fluidity and workability. The strength and durability of concrete increase with decreasing water content. The disadvantages of superplasticisers when added to the concrete in large quantities are causing delay and bleeding in the hardening of the concrete and entering a high amount of air [12,13,14].

The use of lignosulfonate as a superplasticisers was developed in the 1930s. Lignosulfonate is a byproduct of the pulp and paper industry and is derived from lignin, a natural polymer found in wood and other plant materials. Lignosulfonate superplasticizers are very effective in reducing the viscosity of concrete, making it easier to pour and shape. In the middle of the 20th century, research into the development of superplasticizers continued. In the 1960s, the use of naphthalene-based superplasticizers was developed [15]. These additives were found to be very effective in reducing the water-cement ratio in concrete, increasing its strength and durability. Melamine sulfonate plasticizer additives are melamine-based super plasticizers in powder form, which reduce the mixing water in cement and gypsum-based materials and provide high fluidity properties, reduce the water/cement ratio of concrete, increase its early strength, are suitable for use even at low temperatures. These powder plasticizer derivatives are widely used in the production of cement-based powder construction chemicals, repair mortars, injection mortars, ceramic adhesives and joints, grout-anchor-mounting mortars, and leveling screeds. However, it is also widely used in the production of gypsum-based powder building materials, gypsum-based plasters-gypsum board panels, etc.

In the 1980s, a new type of superplasticisers based on polycarboxylate chemistry was developed. Polycarboxylate superplasticisers effectively reduce the water-cement ratio in concrete, providing higher strength and durability while reducing the amount of cement needed [8]. The most effective superplasticisers on the workability is the polycarboxylate ether-based, compared with the traditional sulphonate-based superplasticisers [16].

Within the scope of this study, it is aimed to examine and compare the rheological properties of 2 different superplasticisers, polycarboxylate and melamine sulphonate additives. The tests and investigations within the scope of the study were carried out according to the principles stipulated in TS EN 13813 "Screed Materials and Screeds Applied to Ground-Screed Materials- Properties and Requirements". From the research findings, which type of superplasticising powder additive produces more suitable results for these mortar combinations and the advantages and disadvantages of the use of additives are discussed comparatively.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials Used in Test Samples

In this study, 0.5-1 mm standard sand and 100 µm quartz sand, classified by square mesh sieves, and high density expanded clay aggregate below 2 mm in size were used as aggregate materials. In order to increase the workability and strength of mortar mixtures, 2 types of plasticising additives as polycarboxylate and melamine sulphonate based were used. These additives are new generation superplasticisers in powder form, which can be used at low temperatures, are white in colour, easily soluble in water and have an average density of $550 \pm 50 \text{ kg/m}^3$. CEM I 42.5R Portland cement was used as the main binder material and city mains water was used as the mixed water.

2.2 Use of Material Ratios and Preparation of Samples

In all mixtures prepared within the scope of the study, the total solid amount was kept constant as 1000 grams. Mixture water ratio was kept constant in some of the mixtures, while in the other mixtures, the spreading ratios were changed to be equal or similar. In order to determine the optimum superplasticiser additive ratio, mixtures using two different polycarboxylates, 0.47% and 0.55% of the cement weight, were prepared. However, within the scope of another series of studies, two different mixtures using melamine sulfonate were prepared at 1.5% and 2% of the cement weight. Among the other components in the mixture combinations, 209.6 g of quartz sand with 100 micron grain size and 209.6 g of 0.5-1 mm standard sand in equal amounts were used in each mixture series. The main variable in mixture combinations is the usage rates of 0-2 mm sized expanded clay and cement as

components. In the experimental study, 20% and 30% cement ratios were used, respectively, in the preparation of self-compacting mortar samples.

In experiments, a total of 8 different mix designs were made within the scope of the study in order to analyse the effect of the use of 2 different types of superplasticiser additives used for cement based self-compacting mortars on the performance of the mortar and the mixture components are given in Table 1 and Table 2 as the amount of materials used for 1000 g mortar production.

Table 1. Mixture design using polycarboxylate superplasticiser

Mix Code	Cement (by weight, %)	0.5-1 mm Standard sand (by weight, %)	100 µm Quartz sand (by weight, %)	0-2 mm Expanded clay (by weight, %)	Polycarboxylate superplasticiser	W/C Ratio
P1	30	20,96	20,96	27,94	0,141	0,813
P2	30	20,96	20,96	27,92	0,165	0,813
P3	20	20,96	20,96	37,99	0,094	1,445
P4	20	20,96	20,96	37,97	0,110	1,445

Table 2. Mixture design using melamine sulphonate superplasticiser

Mix Code	Cement (by weight, %)	0.5-1 mm Standard sand (by weight, %)	100 µm Quartz sand (by weight, %)	0-2 mm Expanded clay (by weight, %)	Melamine sulphonate superplasticiser	W/C Ratio
M1	30	20,96	20,96	27,63	0,45	0,88
M2	30	20,96	20,96	27,48	0,6	0,88
M3	20	20,96	20,96	37,78	0,3	1,595
M4	20	20,96	20,96	37,68	0,4	1,595

According to these mixture designs, the materials in the mixture were mixed for approximately 5 minutes until a homogenous powder form was obtained. Afterwards, mixing water was added to the mixture until a suitable spreading condition was found and mixing was continued and a homogeneous mixture was obtained without agglomeration. The average flow diameter of the mixture was determined by measuring the spreading diameters of the fresh mortar obtained from at least three different points on the flow table. In order to test the conformity of the test samples with the parameters such as compressive strength and water absorption stipulated in TS EN 13813 standard 3 samples for each additive type and each additive ratio were prepared separately as specified in TS EN 13892-1 and 50x50x50 mm³ cube sample moulds were used.

All test specimens were demoulded after 1 days and then kept in a humid environment for 7 days. After the 7th day, the specimens were kept in the laboratory at normal room temperature. Unit volume weight values of fresh wet mortar after mixing were measured. In addition, the consistency values of each fresh mortar mixture after mixing were measured by flow table method. In the compressive strength test, the upper and lower surface plates of the test apparatus were wiped with a clean cloth and the specimen was placed in the test apparatus using the adjustment device in such a way that the load was applied to the lower surface during casting and the tests were performed.

3. Research Findings

Some analysis findings of the test samples prepared in different alternative mixture designs for the purpose of analyzing the effect of the plasticizer additive ratio and type on the performance of the mortar in the production of cement-based self-leveling mortar are given in Table 3, respectively.

It was observed that as the amount of cement decreased in both plasticizer types, the flow values of the fresh mortar decreased. As a result, it was determined that the self-leveling performance of the resulting mortar consistency decreased. The contributing factor to this is the decrease in cement content, which reduces the superplasticiser additive dosage, thus reducing the water demand and the flow value of the mortar. It was observed that the change in dispersion values was due to the use of different water ratios depending on the equivalent plasticizer type. Self-leveling flow values in fresh mortar consistencies vary between 200 and 320 mm in mortars with polycarboxylate superplasticiser additives and between 130 and 270 mm in mixtures with melamine sulfonate additives.

Table 3. Test results of mortar in the production of cement-based self-leveling mortar

Mix Code	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Compressive strength at 28 days of curing (N/mm ²)	Capillarity (kg/(m ² *min ^{0.5}))	Water absorption by weight (%)	Apparent porosity (%)
P1	1686	21,01	0,18	5,16	17,92
P2	1795	25,46	0,17	4,93	17,41
P3	1721	12,27	0,26	8,37	21,56
P4	1739	11,38	0,3	10,76	24,25
M1	1889	16,83	0,05	1,82	14,06
M2	1846	14,98	0,07	2,18	14,48
M3	1725	10,87	0,19	8,84	18,7
M4	1687	10,38	0,15	6,36	16,01

When the density values of the hardened mortar samples after 28 days of curing are examined, the density values of the mortar samples using polycarboxylate plasticizer vary between 1686 - 1795 kg/m³. Increasing the amount of polycarboxylate plasticizer in the mortar combination caused an increase in the density value due to the increasing amount of mixing water, albeit at a low level. The opposite of this phenomenon was observed in melamine sulfonate-based mixtures, and density values varied between 1687 - 1889 kg/m³. Increasing the amount of melamine sulfonate plasticizer in the mortar combination caused a decrease in the density value due to the increasing amount of mixing water. The development of this phenomenon was evaluated as an increase in the apparent porosity rate of the mortar obtained in the test findings. The density changes of the mortar samples in the dry state after 28 days of curing are given graphically in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Unit volume weights of the test samples

Another analysis within the scope of the study is to examine the compressive strength values of mortar samples after 28 days. While the compressive strength values of the mortar samples using polycarboxylate plasticizer varied between 11.38 - 25.46 N/mm², it was determined that the strength values of the mortar samples using melamine sulphate plasticizer varied between 10.38 - 16.83 N/mm². In mortar samples prepared at an equivalent cement usage rate, it was determined that the compressive strength of mixtures using polycarboxylate plasticizer additive was higher than those based on melamine sulfonate plasticizer. However, it is also seen that the compressive strength values of mortar designs using the same derivative plasticizer additive lose strength due to decreasing cement ratio. It has been observed that the factor that is effective in this is especially the change in the w/c ratio, and it has been determined that the strength values decrease with an exponential functional approach as the W/C ratio increases in the mixture combination (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Compressive strength versus W/C ratio for test samples

Capillary water absorption values of all test samples were analyzed and it was observed that the use of melamine sulfonate plasticizer played a more effective role in terms of capillarity in the mortar matrix. While the capillary water absorption values of the mortar samples using polycarboxylate plasticizer varied between 0.17 – 0.30 kg/(m²*min^{0.5}), the capillary water absorption values of the mortar samples using melamine sulfonate plasticizer varied between 0,05 – 0,19 kg/(m²*min^{0.5}). Decreasing the cement ratio in mortar mixtures using both derivative plasticizers causes an increase in the capillary water permeability value of the mortar. Another examination in terms of the water resistance of the mortar was considered as the mass water absorption values under normal atmospheric pressure. Similar to the capillarity trend in terms of water absorption values by mass, it was observed that the use of melamine sulphamate plasticizer played a more effective role in terms of water absorption in the mortar matrix (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Water absorption of test samples

As can be seen when Figure 3 is examined, it was determined that the water absorption values of the mortar samples using polycarboxylate plasticizer varied between 4.93% and 10.76%, while the water absorption values of the mortar samples using melamine sulfonate plasticizer varied between 1.82% and 8.84%. The decrease in cement ratio in mortar mixtures using both derivative plasticizers caused an increase in the water absorption value of the mortar. When this situation was examined in detail, it was concluded that the hardened mortar was caused by the difference in porosity phenomenon. Increasing apparent porosity in the mortar matrix caused an increase in the capillary and mass water absorption values of the mortar, too. The apparent porosity values of the test samples are given in Figure 4. While the apparent porosity values of the mortar samples using polycarboxylate plasticizer varied between 17.41% and 24.25%, it was determined that the apparent porosity values of the mortar samples using melamine sulphamate plasticizer varied between 14.06% and 18.70%. The decrease in cement ratio in mortar mixtures using both derivative plasticizers caused an increase in the porosity of the mortar.

Figure 4. Apparent porosity of test samples

4. Results

In this study, improvements have been made on the optimum usage and differences for cement based self-compacting mortars with different types and usage rates of plasticizers. According to these findings,

1. When the consistency analyses of the mixture samples used were examined in detail, it was observed that among the two types of superplasticizers (melamine sulfonate and polycarboxylate) used in the experiment, polycarboxylate based superplasticizer provided more fluidity and self-setting properties than melamine sulfonate based superplasticizer.
2. In the context of the change in compressive strength values of the hardened mortar, higher strength values can be obtained in mortars with polycarboxylate-based additives compared to those with melamine sulfonate additives. It has been determined that polycarboxylate based admixture is more effective in terms of mortar strength.
3. Polycarboxylate-added mortars provided higher strength than melamine sulfonate-added mixtures due to the lower water/cement ratio. In all mortar mixtures, the strength increased due to the increase in cement ratio.
4. In the context of the change in capillary water absorption and mass water absorption values of the hardened mortar, it has been observed that mortars with melamine sulphate-based additives provide lower water absorption performance compared to those with polycarboxylate additives. In the context of the water resistance feature of mortar mixture designs, the use of melamine sulphate-based additives becomes important.
5. It has been observed that the polycarboxylate additive increases the porosity of the mortars by entraining more air in the mortar matrix compared to the melamine sulfonate additive, and accordingly, it increases the water absorption potential of the hardened mortar samples.

References

- [1] O. Rykhlitska, T. Kropyvnytska, (2022), Effect Of Polycarboxylate Superplasticizers on the properties of ready-mix concrete, *Theory and Building Practice*, Vol. 4, No. 1, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.23939/jtbp2022.01.043>
- [2] S. U. Khan, M. F. Nuruddin, T. Ayub, and N. Shafiq, (2014), "Effects of different mineral admixtures on the properties of fresh concrete," *Sci. World J.*, vol. 2014, 2014, doi: 10.1155/2014/986567.
- [3] D. Kumar Nayak, P P Abhilash, R. Singh, R. Kumar, V. Kumar (2022), Compatibility of Ether-Based Poly-Carboxylate Superplasticizer with Mineral Admixtures Blended with OPC. *Civil Engineering and Architecture*, 10(6), 2686 - 2705. DOI: 10.13189/cea.2022.100633.
- [4] A. Frommenwiler, New generation of superplasticizers for high performance concrete (HPC), MBT Holding, Switzerland,
- [5] P.-C. Aïtcin, M. Baalbaki, (1994), Concrete admixtures key components of modern concrete, in A. Aguado, R. Gettu, S.P. Shah (Eds.), *Concrete Technology: New Trends*, Industrial Applications, E&FN Spon, London, 1994, pp. 33-47.
- [6] P.K. Mehta, (1999), *Advances in concrete technology*, *Concr. Int.* 21 (1999) 69-76.

- [7] G. Gelardi, S. Mantellato, D. Marchon, M. Palacios, A.B. Eberhardt, R.J. Flatt, (2016). Chemistry of Chemical Admixtures. P., Aitcin, R. J., Flatt (Ed.). in Science and Technology of Concrete Admixtures (149-281). Amsterdam: Woodhead Publishing.
- [8] Kh. Kamilov, D. R. Abdazov, (2023), Superplasticizers for mortars and concretes. review article, central Asian journal of mathematical theory and computer sciences, Volume: 04, Issue: 6, Jun 2023, ISSN: 2660-5309, <https://cajmtcs.centralasianstudies.org>
- [9] M. Pagé and N. Spiratos, (2000), The Role of Superplasticizers in The Development of Environmentally-Friendly Concrete, Two-Day CANMET/ACI International Symposium on Concrete Technology for Sustainable Development, Vancouver, BC, Canada, April 19-20, 2000
- [10] J. Zolanki, M. Gupta, P. Gurha, S. Agrawal, (2020), Effects of chemicals as superplasticizer on various properties of the concrete, International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT), 2020 IJCRT | Volume 8, Issue 6 June 2020, p 4360 – 4369, ISSN: 2320-2882, IJCRT2006593, www.ijcrt.org
- [11] G. Bye, P. Livesey, L. Struble (2011), Admixtures and Special Cement. Portland Cement: Third edition. doi:10.1680/pc.36116.185
- [12] A. Hallal, E. H. Kadri, K. Ezziane, A. Kadri, and H. Khelafi, (2010), “Combined effect of mineral admixtures with superplasticizers on the fluidity of the blended cement paste,” *Constr. Build. Mater.*, vol. 24, no. 8, pp. 1418–1423, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2010.01.015.
- [13] Li, Z., (2011). *Advanced Concrete Technology*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 70-72, New Jersey, US.
- [14] D. T. Algan, E. Ariöz, Ö. M. Koçkar, (2022), The Effect of Admixture Percent of Sulfonate-Based Admixtures on Mechanical and Microstructural Properties of Cement Mortars. *European Journal of Science and Technology*, (36), 147-150.
- [15] A. Torres, F. Aguayo, S. Allena, M. Ellis, (2020), The Effect of Various Polynaphthalene Sulfonate Based Superplasticizers on the Workability of Reactive Powder Concrete, *Journal of Building Material Science*, 2 (1), 24-30.
- [16] M. Hussein F., Altai S., G. Sami A. (2022), Workability Adjustment And Sensitivity Of Different Fine Cement Mixtures To Polycarboxylate Ether-Based Superplasticizer, *Journal of Applied Engineering Science*, 20(2), 432 - 439, DOI:10.5937/jaes0-34663